

NURSING CARE IN DISEASES OF THE BLOOD AND BLOOD-FORMING ORGANS

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ANNOTATION: This article covers nursing care in diseases of blood and blood-forming organs.

KEYWORDS: Blood system, anemia, leukemia, Hemorrhagic diatheses.

Blood system includes bone marrow, lymph nodes, spleen - blood-forming organs. Here, blood-forming elements: erythrocytes are produced mainly in the red bone marrow, leukocytes - in the spleen and lymph nodes (one form of leukocytes is produced in the spleen - monocytes are produced in the lymph nodes - lymphatics), platelets - in the red bone marrow.

Blood delivers nutrients to all cells of the body and removes harmful products. Blood consists of the clear liquid that remains after the removal of plasma-shaped elements from the blood. The total amount of blood in a healthy human body is about 5 liters. Blood plasma is water, in which proteins, sugar, very small fat particles, various salts, and oxygen (in smaller quantities) are dissolved.

Blood contains up to $5 \times 10^{12}/l$ erythrocytes. They give the blood a red color, because it holds a specific hemoglobin substance. Erythrocytes passing through the lungs with blood, due to their unique structure (in particular, iron is included in hemoglobin), take oxygen and transport it to all organs and tissues.

The lifespan of erythrocytes is about 1 month, they are broken down more in the spleen (less often in the liver, bone marrow), so the spleen is called the "grave" of erythrocytes.

Hemoglobin released after erythrocyte destruction is a component of bilirubin produced by the liver, iron is used for the "construction" of new erythrocytes.

Leukocytes are able to move (amoebic movements), they can digest substances foreign to the body, for example, dead cells (phagocytosis).

Leukocytes, unlike erythrocytes, retain a cell nucleus. There are leukocytes in the blood normally from $3.2 \times 10^9/l$ to $11.3 \times 10^9/l$. Organulocytes are lymphocytes and monocytes.

In relation to the total number of leukocytes, granulocytes make up approximately 60-65%, lymphocytes - 19-37%, monocytes - 3-11%, acidophilic granuladites - 2%, basophilic granuladites - 0-1.0%.

Thrombocytes participate in blood clotting. Normally, their amount is from $180.0 \times 10^9/l$ to $320.0 \times 10^9/l$ or 50 platelets per 1000 erythrocytes.

Anemia. Among the diseases of blood formation organs, anemia or anemia is common. In this pathological condition, the amount of hemoglobin and erythrocytes in the blood is mostly reduced.

Anemia - a lot of blood loss (for example, during an injury), a decrease in the function of red bone marrow, a lack of substances necessary for blood formation processes in the body, especially cyanocobalamin or iron, and also due to an infectious-toxin effect on the bone marrow. can be liq.

Hypochromic and hyperchromic anemia are distinguished according to the blood color index. (hyperchromic anemia is characterized by a high color index of blood, unlike hypochromic anemia, the amount of hemoglobin in the blood decreases to a lesser extent compared to the amount of erythrocytes). In the mechanism of the development of a number of anemias, the decrease in the regenerative properties of red bone marrow is considered a common link. The continuous loss of the bone marrow's ability to produce erythrocytes leads to the rapid development of anemia. The patient may die because of this or from the infection that has been added to it.

Currently, the most common types of anemia with a unique clinical picture are distinguished: Posthemorrhagic anemia occurs as a result of blood loss.

Iron deficiency anemia develops due to iron deficiency in the body.

Pernicious anemia is due to lack of antianemic factor (cyanicobalamin).

Hemolytic anemia occurs from the breakdown of erythrocytes.

Hypoplastic anemia develops due to decreased bone marrow function.

Leukosis.

Leukemia is the general name for blood-forming cells that damage the bone marrow. The etiology of the disease is unknown, and its course resembles the development of a malignant tumor. There are speculations about the viral nature of leukemia.

The essence of leukemia is damage to the bone marrow, spleen, and lymph nodes. In leukemia, a large number of immature leukocytes are observed in the peripheral blood, which are usually found only in the bone marrow and lymph nodes. In some cases, the total amount of leukocytes in the peripheral blood does not increase, they only change in quality. Such leukemias are called aleukemic leukemias. Acute and chronic leukemia are distinguished.

Hemorrhagic diatheses

Hemorrhagic diathesis is characterized by increased blood flow spontaneously or as a result of some minor injuries. Blood clotting is a complex process, in which there are 3 main groups of factors that cause bleeding.

In the process of blood clotting, the amount of platelets decreases. They are of the main importance in bringing blood-clotting plasma factors to the place of bleeding and stopping the bleeding. The last type is characterized by the transition of soluble protein (fibrinogen) to insoluble protein (fibrin) under the action of a specific enzyme-thrombin based on blood coagulation. Depending on the sign of pathogenesis, all hemorrhagic diatheses are divided into three groups:

Hemorrhagic diatheses with disorders of blood clotting properties (hemophilia, K-avitaminosis). Hemorrhagic diatheses with impaired vascular function. Hemorrhagic diatheses caused by disorders of thrombocytopoiesis (Werlhof's disease, leukemia, light disease

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